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Despite the computing power achieved with current technologies, computationally intensive analyses (e.g. optimization problems, reliability or sensitivity analyses) actually remain a time-consuming problem in modern engineering. Traditionally, a widely used approach to deal with this issue based on learning from data, relies on metamodels or surrogate modeling. As a result, the emulator has the attraction of being fast to evaluate. In this context, metamodels based on Kriging (a.k.a. Gaussian Process (GP)) have gained momentum in computational sciences by playing a crucial role in the expansion of machine learning tools. The specific objective of this study is to investigate the use of different Python libraries for Kriging metamodeling purposes, setting out a consistently review of the major frameworks used in the engineering field. In particular, a focus on two primary aims is addressed: (a) to compare the various settings available for each library; (b) to ascertain how they perform and differ under similar assumptions. In this investigation, the aim is to be of value to practitioners wanting to know on the capability and reliability of the multitude of open-source packages available nowadays.

Keywords: Kriging, Gaussian Process, Surrogate, Metamodel, Python, Machine Learning.

1. Introduction

1.1. General considerations

In recent years, various computer codes have reached a high level of sophistication enabling extremely accurate simulations in describing the physical behavior of a given system. This increase in accuracy occurs, however, at the expense of time efficiency. In fact, the repetitive solution of computationally intensive analyses is usually required in typical engineering problems (e.g. optimization problems, reliability or sensitivity analyses), and actually remains a time-consuming limit despite the current computing performances of nowadays. Many literature evidence attest the effectiveness in the use of metamodels (a.k.a. surrogates) to deal with this issue (Dubourg et al. (2013), Moustapha et al. (2021)). Essentially, they rely on approximating the physical models by easy-to-evaluate mathematical functions.

Kriging is a stochastic interpolation method based on learning from data by incorporating prior knowledge (Williams and Rasmussen (2006)). Its origins can be found in spatial-geostatistics (Matheron (1963)) for obtaining the best linear unbiased estimator given available measurements. During the last two decades, it has been reformulated in the context of Bayesian inference, gaining momentum in the realm of machine learning toolboxes. In the latter context, Kriging is also known as Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and the two terms are used interchangeably. Its application spectrum goes from simple regression to classification and clustering tasks (Kim and Lee (2007), Kapoor et al. (2010)). In regression problems, Kriging offers, for a given set of training data samples, a solution to the potentially infinitely functions that fit the data by assigning a probability to each of these functions. The most probable characteriza-

tion of the data subsequently coincides with the mean of this distribution. Due to its probabilistic nature, this metamodel also allows to incorporate the uncertainty in the prediction into the regression result (Görtler et al. (2019)). Kriging popularity is mainly related to its features: (a) it is exact on the experimental design samples (ED) under suitable assumptions; (b) it provides a prediction of the model outcome at a given point (Kriging mean); (c) it provides the user with an additional information, the Kriging variance, which might be used as a metric for the precision error. As a matter of fact, a large and growing body of literature has investigated the latter peculiarity to locally reduce uncertainties by adaptively adding extra-points in the design of experiments (a.k.a. Active-Learning methods), improving the Kriging’s accuracy and efficiency (Jones et al. (1998), Echard et al. (2011), Lelièvre et al. (2018)). The benefit of this approach explains the success of its diffusion in many fields of application, from aerospace design to earthquake engineering, and mechanical engineering, leading to the release of several GP toolboxes over the last two decades (Erickson et al. (2018)).

1.2. Motivation

The purpose of this study is to investigate the use of different Python libraries for Kriging meta-modeling. To date, there is very little published information on it, and no large-scale studies have been conducted. A systematic understanding of how different Python toolboxes perform remains largely unexamined. Consequently, the role of this work is to set out a consistently review of the major frameworks used by engineers, with the specific objective of filling this gap. In this investigation, the aim is to be of value to practitioners wanting to know on the capability and reliability of the multitude of open-source packages available nowadays.

In addition to a discussion on the theoretical background behind the capabilities of the toolboxes, a focus on two primary aims is addressed: (a) to compare the various settings available for each library; (b) to ascertain how they perform and differ under similar assumptions. More precisely, the main features, options, as well as the optimization algorithms, the estimation methods,

the trend’s functional basis and the correlation models available for each toolbox, are described in a detailed full-comprehensive comparative table providing a general overview on the investigated Python packages. The latter are then compared revealing similarity and dissimilarity in their behavior using different data sets and case studies based on a practical Finite Element (FE) benchmark. Specifically, a formal comparison is carried out on the prediction accuracy by means of Mean of the Squared Errors (MSE). Furthermore, a well-known issue of Kriging metamodels lies on its computation complexity for large data, implying time-consuming problems. Consequently, a comparison on computational time-cost is pointed out for different size of ED, and constitutes the last type of discrepancy among the studied tools.

2. Theoretical foundations

In this section, we explore some theoretical foundations on which Gaussian Processes are built on.

The basic building block consists in assuming that the Kriging metamodel is a realization of a Gaussian Process. Practically, this means that each input random variable $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d\}^T$ is distributed normally and their joint probability is also Gaussian. In this way, one can define the multivariate Gaussian distribution by a mean function $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ and a covariance function $C(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ (see e.g. Williams and Rasmussen (2006)):

$$Y(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mu(\mathbf{x}), C(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')) \quad (1)$$

Following e.g. Santner et al. (2003), and Lantiotis et al. (2021), the Kriging metamodel can be described finally as follows:

$$Y(\mathbf{x}) = \beta^T \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + Z(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

where β_j are unknown parameters, f_j are known arbitrary functional basis, and the term $\beta^T \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ represents the GP trend (i.e. its mean value); whereas $Z(\mathbf{x})$ is a mean zero, second-order stationary Gaussian process with variance σ^2 .

In addition, we assume:

$$cov(Z(\mathbf{x}), Z(\mathbf{x}')) = \sigma^2 R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'; \theta) \quad (3)$$

where $R(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}'; \theta)$ is a correlation function that describes the correlation between two sample points

\mathbf{x} , \mathbf{x}' , and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_d\}^\top$ are unknown parameters (referred to as the correlation parameters or hyperparameters) that need to be estimated from the available data setting up an optimization problem.

2.1. Prediction with noise-free data

In the case that the observations are noise free, the joint Gaussian distribution incorporating the knowledge of the training data given the observation \mathbf{Y} to the Kriging prediction Y_0 of a new point \mathbf{x} is given by (see for instance Dubourg (2011)):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Y_0 \\ \mathbf{Y} \end{Bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ \mathbf{F} \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{Bmatrix}, \sigma^2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{r}_0^\top \\ \mathbf{r}_0 & \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the observation matrix of the Kriging trend, \mathbf{f}_0 is the vector of regressors evaluated at \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{r}_0 is the vector of cross-correlations, and \mathbf{R} is the correlation matrix of the observations.

2.2. Prediction using noisy data

More realistic is the case where the data are noisy, that is $Y = \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon$ (Lataniotis et al. (2021)). Assuming additive independent identically distributed Gaussian noise ε with variance Σ_n (i.e., $\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_n)$), the joint Gaussian distribution for the noisy observations now becomes:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Y_0 \\ \mathbf{Y} \end{Bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_0^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ \mathbf{F} \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \sigma^2 & \sigma^2 \mathbf{r}_0^\top \\ \sigma^2 \mathbf{r}_0 & \sigma^2 \mathbf{R} + \Sigma_n \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (5)$$

2.3. The best linear unbiased predictor

The best linear unbiased predictor (a.k.a. universal Kriging predictor) of the unobserved quantity Y_0 is the Gaussian random variate $\hat{Y}_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{\hat{Y}_0}, \sigma_{\hat{Y}_0}^2)$.

Predictions at new points can be made in terms of the mean and variance of \hat{Y}_0 . In the case of noise-free data (Section 2.1), the Kriging predictor is an interpolant with respect to the experimental design points, whereas it is a regression model in the case of noisy data (Section 2.2).

2.4. Correlation functions, Estimation methods and Optimization algorithms

The correlation function (a.k.a. kernel or covariance function) contains the assumptions about the approximation function, describing the similarity

between observations and new points. Two categories of kernels can be distinguished: stationary and non-stationary kernels. The first ones depend only on the distance of two data points. The second ones depend also on the specific values of the data points. Stationary kernels can further be subdivided into *isotropic* kernels in which only a single scale parameter θ is associated with all the input dimensions, and *anisotropic* kernels whose scale parameter is unique for each input dimension. However, whatever the kernel choice, the hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ need to be estimated by solving an optimization problem that differs depending on the selected estimation method, and whether the responses are noisy or not. The most common estimation approach is based on maximizing the likelihood of the observations. However, regarding the solution of optimization problems, there are mainly three approaches one can follow: local methods (generally gradient-based) which tend to converge faster, but which can perform inadequately especially for increasing input dimension when the existence of multiple local minima may occur; global methods; or hybrid methods that combine the features of both approaches.

3. Overview of Python packages for GP

This section provides a general overview on the packages used in our study. Table 1 lists the principal packages examined and their main features.

3.1. Packages overview

`scikit-learn` (Pedregosa et al. (2011)) is a well-known Python package for broad spectrum machine-learning. Within the context of GPs, it allows to solve regression (GPR) and probabilistic classification problems (GPC).

`SMT` (Bouhrel et al. (2019)) is meant to be a general library for surrogate modeling whose focus is on derivatives to be used for gradient-based optimization.

`OpenTURNS` (Baudin et al. (2015)) and `UQ[py]Lab` (Lataniotis et al. (2021)), two softwares dedicated to general-purpose uncertainty quantification, both implement Kriging metamodeling. It is worth to mention that `UQ[py]Lab` is a software binding developed for Python based

Table 1. Comparison of main Python libraries for Kriging (• stands for feature availability; × for default settings).

Package	scikit-learn	UQ[py]Lab	OpenTURNS	SMT	GPy	GPflow	GPyTorch
Reference	Pedregosa et al. (2011)	Lataniotis et al. (2021)	Baudin et al. (2015)	Bouhlef et al. (2019)	GPy (2012)	Matthews et al. (2017)	Gardner et al. (2018)
License	BSD	MIT	GNU LGPL	BSD	BSD	Apache	MIT
Release	v1.0.2	v0.2 Beta	v1.18	v1.1.0	v1.10.0	v.2.4.0	v1.6.0
Trend types							
<i>Simple Kriging</i>	×	•			×	×	•
<i>Ordinary Kriging</i>		×	•	×		•	•
<i>Universal Kriging</i>		•	•				•
<i>Linear</i>		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Quadratic</i>		•	•	•			
<i>Polynomial</i>		•					
<i>Custom</i>		•				•	•
Kernel Families							
<i>Constant</i>	•					•	•
<i>Linear</i>	•	•			•	•	•
<i>Exponential</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Gaussian (RBF)</i>	•	•	•	×	×	•	•
<i>Matérn</i>	•	×	•	•	•	•	•
<i>White</i>	•				•	•	•
<i>Periodic</i>	•				•	•	•
<i>Others</i>	•		•		•	•	•
<i>Custom</i>	•	•	•			•	•
Kernel mixture	•		•		•	•	
Isotropic/Anisotropic	•	•	•		•	•	•
Estimation methods							
<i>Maximum-likelihood</i>	×	•	•	×	×	•	•
<i>Cross-validation</i>		×					
Optimization methods							
<i>L-BFGS</i>	×	•			×	×	
<i>GA</i>		•					
<i>HGA</i>		×					
<i>CMA-ES / HCMA-ES</i>		•					
<i>COBYLA</i>	•		•	×	•	•	
<i>TNC</i>	•		×	•	•	•	
<i>SLSQP / Newton-CG</i>	•				•	•	
<i>Others</i>	•		•		•	•	•
<i>Custom</i>	•				•	•	
Number of restarts	×	×	•	×	×	×	
Nugget	×	×	•	×	•		
Noisy-data	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Normalize ED	•	×		×	•		
Problem type							
<i>Regression (GPR)</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Classification (GPC)</i>	•				•	•	•
<i>Sparse GP / GPLVM</i>					•	•	•
<i>DeepGP</i>						•	•
GPU acceleration					•	•	•

on UQCloud, a version of UQLab that runs on the cloud. Practically, the latter replicates the full UQLab framework in Python without the need of a local Matlab installation. As a consequence, all operations do not take place locally on the machine of the user but in the cloud. At the time of writing, UQ[py]Lab is still in beta version.

GPY (GPY (2012)) from the Sheffield machine learning group is based on gradient computations and offers considerably more setting possibilities than the previous packages.

GPflow (Matthews et al. (2017)), based on the foundations of GPY, implements GP inference for composable kernels and likelihoods. The main difference between GPY and GPflow is that the latter uses TensorFlow for its core computations rather than numeric Python for fast execution on GPUs. Although the GPU functionality is present in GPY is currently limited to CUDA code. On the contrary the GPflow implementation is targeted at a broad variety of GPU capability.

GPYtorch (Gardner et al. (2018)) combines GPs with deep neural networks allowing the efficient training of GPs with very large set of data points. It is implemented in PyTorch with GPU acceleration. It is worth to notice that, although this paper primarily focuses on the regression setting, both GPflow and GPYtorch are also compatible with variational techniques (Non-Gaussian likelihoods).

3.1.1. Correlation functions

In `scikit-learn`, users can specify different kernels. Common kernels are provided including Radial-basis Function (RBF), Gaussian, Matérn, Exp-Sine-Squared, and rational quadratic kernels. It is also possible to specify custom kernels, as well as kernel operators for kernel mixture: sum, product, exponentiation. In addition, including a `WhiteKernel` component into the kernel allows to estimate the noise level of data.

Much higher is the range of the provided kernels for `OpenTURNS`, `GPY`, `GPflow` and `GPYtorch`. From simple standard kernels that produce constant, linear and white noise functions, to stationary functions that produce samples with varying degrees of smoothness, to kernels that produce pe-

riodic samples. Sums and products of kernels are also implemented to create new composite kernels.

In UQ[py]Lab four correlation family are supported: Linear, Exponential, Gaussian, and Matérn, plus one more option for user-defined kernels. It is also possible to define whether the correlation function is isotropic or anisotropic, as well as treat noisy responses.

3.1.2. Estimation and Optimization methods

`scikit-learn` uses as default the L-BFGS-B optimization algorithm from the `SciPy` library with the possibility to set a number of restarts preventing getting stuck in a local minima. Other supported optimizers from the same library can be also specified, or externally defined optimizer can be passed as a callable. Also GPY supports the optimization algorithms from the `SciPy` library, and extends the choice as well to other modules like `climin` and `paramz`. Likewise `scik-itlearn`, it uses as default the L-BFGS-B algorithm and allows to define the number of optimization restarts.

SMT uses the gradient-free optimization algorithm COBYLA. `OpenTURNS` do the same as default, but other choices can be done among other solver like Abdo-Rackwitz, Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP), Truncated Newton Constrained (TNC) and NLOpt solvers.

For all the aforementioned packages, the hyperparameters of the kernel are optimized by maximizing the log-marginal-likelihood (LML) based on the passed optimizer. An additional option is further implemented in UQ[py]Lab: the cross-validation estimation. In addition, this package uses Hybrid Genetic Algorithm (HGA) as optimization method by default. Besides, other options are available: LBFSGS, Genetic Algorithm (GA), CMA-ES and HCMA-ES.

GPflow supports several optimizers both from the `SciPy` optimizer and the natural gradient descent optimizer.

Even though traditional inference approaches require the user to provide routines for computing the full GP marginal log likelihood, GPYtorch only requires access to a black-box routine that performs matrix-matrix multiplications with the

kernel matrix and its derivative (BBMM inference) utilizing GPU acceleration. Avoiding the Cholesky decomposition, consequently, is beneficial, reducing the asymptotic complexity of exact GP inference from $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ to $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$, n being the total number of samples in the calibration set.

4. Comparative study

The concrete differences that one can observe in predicted values when using different libraries are reasonably afferent only to different parameter estimates. Indeed, all the packages compute the predictions using the same equations. However, parameters must be estimated by solving an optimization problem whose solution depends on several factors (i.e, starting values, bounds conditions, the algorithm used) (Erickson et al. (2018)).

In this work, a benchmark case study essentially examines the performance of the optimization methods and their prediction discrepancy for three packages selected among the ones showed in Table 1: `scikit-learn`, `UQ[py]` Lab, `SMT`.

4.1. Methodology

The criteria chosen for the packages comparison are primarily two: the evaluation of the MSE at the validation points $\mathbf{x}^* = \{\mathbf{x}_1^*, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n^*\}$ (Eq. (6)), and the estimation of the computational time.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(Y(\mathbf{x}_i^*) - \hat{Y}(\mathbf{x}_i^*) \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

The first criterion is used to measure the model predictive accuracy by means of a single number that condenses the fitting quality; whereas the second criteria involves two metrics, namely the computational time needed to build and to evaluate the GP model at the validation points. The reason for the latter interest lies in the fact that we want to get Information on how much computational investment is required to see a significant improvement in accuracy.

4.2. Results

In this section we compare the aforementioned Python packages on a benchmark case-study. The latter consists of a FE shell plate model of a rectangular plate with dimension $1.5m \times 1m$. A pressure

of $100 Pa$ is uniformly applied at the surface of the plate and the four edges are clamped. The plate involves multiple plies with equal thickness and equal anisotropic material. Their angles of orientation are treated as random variables. The displacement at the center of the plate (influenced by the plies' orientation due to the material anisotropy) is used as the quantity of interest to calibrate the Kriging metamodel. Several cases involving an increasing number of fiber angles (and so of random variables) are investigated in this study, each one of those matches with a different size of the input problem dimension. Practically, the random vector takes the form: $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$ where $m \in [2, 4, 8, 16, 32]$. For all the case, we generated samples through Monte Carlo simulations using an input space with a uniform distribution between 0° and 180° . In addition, we are also interested in how the toolboxes behave for different ED sizes, simulating in this manner realistic scenarios that take into account different availability of data. Consequently, further sub-cases are investigated with a total size N_{ED} up to the 35% of the total available dataset (20000 points). Thus at the end we have 195 fitted metamodels - three packages fitting thirteen different ED size for five different input dimensions. It is worth mentioning at this point that, to see how libraries differ under similar assumptions, each Kriging metamodel has been constructed using the same Matérn 3/2 correlation function notwithstanding the toolbox examined. Whereas, settings on the optimization algorithm have been left as default.

Fig. 1. Cross-validation plot for SMT, dimension 4.

Fig. 2. MSE at different dimensionality.

Figure 1 pictures one of the cross-validation plots obtained. As it is intuitive to expect, we can appreciate how increasing N_{ED} is qualitatively beneficial for the predictive accuracy of the meta-model.

4.2.1. Mean Squared Error

Regarding the evolution of the MSE with respect to N_{ED} and to the dimensionality of the problem, it appears clear from Figure 2 that the benefits of having large size of ED become minor as the dimensionality of the problem grows up. Hence, for higher dimensions almost the same order of magnitude for the MSE can be achieved at a lower computational cost. Moreover, freezing one dimension leads to Figure 3. This plot represents in particular the evolution of the MSE with respect to N_{ED} for the case of dimension four. It can be concluded from Figure 3 that discrepancies in packages are greater at increasing number of ED. As evidence, the SMT package reaches a better accuracy (up to almost an order of magnitude) than the other toolboxes.

4.2.2. Computational time

The last type of discrepancy among the studied libraries is pointed out from the comparison on computational time-cost in Figure 4. In the latter, two times are plotted: the time t_1 needed to build the GP metamodel, and the time t_2 needed to evaluate the GP at validation points. It can be appreciated how they differ in both durations. In this case,

Fig. 3. MSE for increasing value of N_{ED} . Dimension case: 4.

Fig. 4. MSE vs time. t_1 is the time to build the GP. t_2 is the time to evaluate GP at validation points.

it results that SMT tends to perform quickly than the other packages for higher N_{ED} in calibrating the Kriging model, but not in its evaluation.

5. Conclusions

The focus of this work is centered on reviewing the main Python libraries for Kriging metamodeling purposes. Notwithstanding setting up the same Kriging surrogate with the same kernel on the same input data, discrepancies have been observed among various Python packages tested. The underlying reason can be substantially addressed in how each toolbox esteems the hyper-parameters through the numerical optimization algorithm. Researchers and engineers should be aware that the prediction quality, as well as the computational

time, strongly depends on these algorithms and their settings. The next steps for this research include the extension to more packages as well as the investigation of various other possible scenarios (such exploring other kernel types and other optimization algorithms). This will provide full insights on the most used python libraries for GP making a positive contribution to instil in users a better understanding of their potentiality and capability.

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